

**COMPARATIVE REVIEW OF THE CURRENT STATE OF DESIGN
AND DEVELOPMENT OF AUTONOMOUS INVERTERS**

Sh.B. Umarov

F.A. Akhmadaliyev

Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov

Abstract: The article presents the results of the analysis of the current state and the prospects for the development of methods for designing and developing autonomous inverters.

The division of power semiconductor devices into three groups based on their structural complexity and manufacturing technology is presented. The possible types of electric energy conversion in power electronic converter devices are characterized. A detailed examination of the structural scheme of such autonomous converters is provided, as well as a description of the structure elements and functional blocks. It is shown that the development of new topologies in the field of power electronics entails the development of multi-level and matrix AIT schemes.

The key words: semiconductor devices, standalone current inverters, standalone voltage inverters, resonant inverters.

The stages of development and prospects of the issues in modeling electromagnetic processes in standalone inverters are closely linked to the theoretical and corresponding practical advancement of both semiconductor devices themselves and the energy converters based on them.

The application of power semiconductor devices, depending on their design complexity and manufacturing technology, can be conditionally divided into three groups 1. The first group includes diodes, transistors, and single-operation thyristors, which are used in "traditional" power electronics circuits. The second group comprises fully controllable thyristors with emitter control and integrated driver. The third group consists of high-tech thyristor devices with high level of integration and MOS-control

(IGBT and others), having modular multi-crystalline design with intelligent elements (self-protection, self-testing, etc.).

The development and practical implementation of each successive generation of power semiconductor devices have, in turn, led to the qualitative advancement of converter devices with a corresponding increase in their power and expansion of their application areas. The most intensive development of high-power thyristor devices occurred during the last decades of the 20th century. During these periods, fundamental principles were formulated and prospects for the development of all possible types of electrical energy conversion shown in Figure 1 were defined.

Figure 1 Possible types of electric power conversion

During the stage of using single-operation thyristors as indicated in the figure, standalone DC-AC energy converters were qualitatively divided into standalone current inverters, voltage inverters, and resonant inverters (CI, VI, and RI). Since single-operation thyristors conduct current when triggered by control signals and block current when the anode-cathode circuit is interrupted, practical DC-AC inverter schemes considered numerous options for introducing forced commutation devices, auxiliary valves, additional power sources, protection devices, and others into the power circuits.

The structural diagram of such standalone converters is shown in Fig. 2. The structure elements represent the following functional blocks:

1. F – filter on the direct current side.
2. P – the converter itself, converting direct current into alternating current, consisting of a group of power and commutating thyristors.
3. CM – control system, including a reference generator, pulse distributor for control channels and individual thyristors.
4. IU – intermediate device, coupling the converter to the load. This could be higher harmonic filters for current or voltage, an impedance-matching transformer, and others.
5. BRT – backflow valve unit. This element is present in all standalone inverters. Through BRT, energy exchange between the source and the load is implemented.

Among the listed DC-AC converters, at present, for most types of loads, AI inverters using fully controllable semiconductor devices such as IGCT-controlled thyristors and transistors with insulated gates (IGBTs) are predominantly employed as control devices. However, for loads with active braking mechanisms (centrifuges, test

equipment, cranes, rocking machines, submersible pumps, fluid transfer pump units, and various turbo mechanisms), as well as in heating installations (electric furnaces of various types), and electrolytic installations, the primary preference is given to the use of RI 2, as well as inverters based on controllable thyristors.

As known 3, RI as a representative of the family of DC-AC converters is one of the first developed and implemented types of standalone inverters. In contrast to other types of inverters, it has the following two distinctive features:

1. The input circuit of the inverter must simulate a direct current source, which, by periodically switching the valves in the output circuits, changes the current direction at the load nodes, thus generating alternating current at the output.

2. The load of the RI must possess a resulting impedance of a capacitive nature in order to facilitate the abrupt change of current at the load nodes. This is practically achieved by including a commutating capacitor at the output of the valve block.

The classical parallel RI scheme has the following drawbacks: a sharply dropping external characteristic, limited stability, inability to achieve low frequencies due to discharging of capacitors through parallel circuits, and the inability to regulate frequency over wide ranges.

To address these drawbacks, additional capacitors are connected to the outputs of the RI, snubber valves and backflow valves (BFV) are introduced, and the schemes are complemented with thyristor-inductive regulators 3, 4. Figure 3 shows the scheme of a single-phase parallel RI supplemented with the mentioned attributes. If necessary, similar additional elements can be used in three-phase schemes.

The capacitors in these schemes, connected in parallel to the load, only operate during the current commutation in the load phases (hence they are called commutating). The capacitance values are independent of the reactive power of the load, ensuring that the RI can operate with any load and at any output voltage frequency within the commutating capacity of the capacitors.

Figure 3 Scheme of a single-phase parallel RI with CM

The development of converter units based on fully controllable thyristors has led to a significant increase in the development and implementation of high-power electronic devices. This is evidenced by the sharp increase in the level of sales in the global market of power semiconductor devices, which rose from 4.94 billion US dollars in 1996 to 11 billion in 2001 and 18 billion in 2010. According to the forecast of the German statistical firm Statista GmbH, a substantial increase in the market for sales of automotive inverters based on metal-oxide semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) is expected in the period from 2018 to 2029. For example, if the sales level in 2018 amounted to 121.6 million US dollars, then by 2029, this figure is expected to increase approximately 68 times, reaching 8.3 billion US dollars. Such intense development of the power electronics component base contributes to the increase in specific power of the implemented converters, significantly expanding the range of operational, technical, and economic characteristics.

The stages of development of high-power device technology, the expansion of power and frequency ranges of their use, as well as the high demand for them in the global market, have led to the development of AI circuit topologies and valve converters in general. The prospects of "new" topologies lie in the development of AI circuits based on the synthesis of the harmonic composition of the output voltages and currents of inverters. It should be noted that the idea of forming any complex form of

output voltages and currents of AI with improved harmonic composition has been used before, based on powerful bipolar and MOSFET transistors; however, the power range and interest in such converters were limited to units of kilowatts.

The development of new topologies in the direction of high-power electronics involves the development of multi-level and matrix AI circuits. Multi-level converters, for the purpose of improving the harmonic composition, involve increasing the number of stages in the forms of output voltages of inverters, while matrix converters - single-level AI, perform the same functions of improving the quality of the output voltage forms using PWM, PFM, CPWM, etc.

The basic topology of a three-level single-phase AI with controllable thyristors is shown in Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 4 Three-level single-phase AI circuit

The transistorized controllable scheme of a three-level three-phase AI, its control diagrams, phase and line voltages at the load are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Diagram of a transistor three-level single-phase AIT.

Figure 6 shows the diagram of a multi-level three-phase AIT with controllable thyristors.

Figure 6 Diagram of a multi-level three-phase AIT.

The development direction of schematic solutions for matrix converters involves the installation of capacitor filters on the side of the input voltage, the load, or on both sides simultaneously. Such conditions arise due to the necessity of organizing stable valve commutation during PWM or other types of modulation. A typical frequency converter circuit based on AIT with PWM is shown in Figure7.

Figure 7 Typical diagram of a frequency converter based on AIT with PWM

The PWM-AIT converter shown is manufactured by Power Flex 7000 Allen Bradley. The converter is designed using SGCT thyristors (symmetrical gate commutated thyristors with integrated control). This VSD operates at a higher modulation frequency: 440-1000 Hz (compared to 200-225 Hz for GTO thyristors). This parameter ensures a higher coefficient of sinusoidality of the inverted current and voltage waveforms.

In addition to the aforementioned schematic solutions, one of the most promising directions in the development of power electronics today is the development and application of intelligent power modules. This is due to the constant improvement of manufacturing technology and the enhancement of technical characteristics of powerful field-effect transistors - MOSFET and IGBT, and highly integrated power drivers 6. The companies that are most successful in this direction are Mitsubishi, Fairchild, International Rectifier, Siemens, Schorch, BM Elektronik, Transrech Antriebs systeme Berlin, Relience Elektrik, Germany; "Hill Graham Control", USA; "Asi Robicon", Italy - USA; "Alstom", France; "Allen Bradley", USA-Canada; ESTEL PLUS, Estonia; NPP "EOS", Ukraine, etc. Fig. 8 shows the intelligent power module AUIRS2334S - 600 from International Rectifier (USA): a) schematic diagram; b) external view.

Figure 8 Intelligent power module: a) schematic diagram; b) external view

Thus, the stages and prospects of development of valve converters in general and autonomous current inverters (AIT) in particular, as presented in the review, allow us to assess the current state of issues related to the design, manufacturing, and implementation of high-efficiency DC-AC converters.

Conclusions

1. The development of AIT in the context of its use in various electromechanical, electrotechnical, and electrical engineering devices has continued throughout history, starting from the turbulent stages of the idea of converting DC to AC (beginning in the 1930s). Particularly noteworthy is the development of AIT in the 1960s, the years of intensive implementation of thyristor technology.

2. Each DC-AC converter in the series performs the function of electromagnetically coupling current sources or EMFs with the load. The substantial interest of major European and global companies in the design and development of

AIT demonstrates that there is a wide class of loads for which power sources and their control with AIT are fundamentally required.

3. The development of high-power semiconductor devices in the last decade of the previous century has led to the emergence of new directions and topologies in the design and implementation of high-efficiency DC-AC converters and various types of inverters within them.

References

1. Surma A.M. State and prospects of development of power semiconductor devices for converter devices // *Electricity*, 2006, No.9. Pp. 21-30
2. Belous A.I., Efimenko S.A., Turtsevich A.S. *Semiconductor power electronics*. -M.: Technosphere, 2013.-216 p.
3. Zabrodin Yu.S. *Industrial electronics: a textbook for universities*. - M.: Alliance, 2013. - 496 p.
4. Zinov'ev G.S. *Power electronics*. - M.: Jurayt, 2015.- 667 p.
5. Malnev A.I., Bakhovtsev I.A., Zinov'ev G.S. Review of multilevel current inverters for wind energy stations // *Proceedings of the Tomsk Polytechnic University. Engineering of Georesources*. 2015. Vol.326. No.7.- Pp. 15-26
6. Lazarev G. High-voltage converters for frequency-controlled electric drive // *Electrical News*, 2019, No.5(119). - Pp.1-15.